

Substituted [1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines and [1,3,4]-thiadiazolidines; synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial study

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Abstract : Series of compounds 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-ethanones and 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-ethanones have been synthesized by the interaction of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido-acetamides with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride respectively. These compounds on acetylation afforded acetyl derivatives. The title compounds have been assayed for their antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative microorganisms.

Keywords : Synthesis, antimicrobial activity, dithiadiazine, thiadiazolidine.

Introduction

Synthesis, structural properties and bacteriocidal as well as fungicidal activities of substituted [1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines¹, [1,4,2,5]-dithiadiazines², [1,4,2,6]-dithiadiazines³, [1,3,4]-thiadiazolidines⁴, [1,2,5]-thiadiazolidines⁵ and [1,2,4]-thiadiazolidines⁶ have been reported earlier in some communications. On perusal of literature, it has been observed that substituted thiadiazolidines have a potential as inhibitors of human leukocyte elastase, cathepsin G and important for their cytotoxicity⁷. It has been also reported earlier that, substituted [1,2,4]-thiadiazolidines inhibit nuclear transcription factor-kB and its dependent genes activation but induces apoptosis⁶. Synthetic applications of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride⁸ and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride⁹ have been investigated earlier and shown to have enough potentiality in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing 5 and 6 membered heterocyclic compounds¹⁰. In view of the utility of these reagents in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds and as a part of wider programme to provide alternative routes of synthesis¹¹, now the method for synthesis of substituted bis-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines and bis-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidines is reported.

Results and discussion

Initially equimolar solution of benzotriazole (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxan and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (4 g) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 h, to afford ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate. Then the parent compound, benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (**1**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in 1,4-dioxan (15 ml) on a water bath for 5 h, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol (5 : 5 v/v) mixture¹².

It was transformed into 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido-acetamides (**3a-h**) by condensing with *N*-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (**2a-h**) (0.01 mol) in refluxing carbontetrachloride medium for 2.5 h.

Compounds (**3a-h**) were reacted separately with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride in boiling chloroform for 3 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was clearly noticed as tested with moist blue litmus paper. Cooling the reaction mixture and distilling off chloroform afforded sticky masses, which on washing with petroleum ether gave granular solids. These were acidic to litmus and on titri-

metric analysis identified as 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-ethanone hydrochlorides (**4a-h**) and 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-ethanone hydrochlorides (**7a-h**). These

on basification with aqueous ammonia solution afforded free bases, (**5a-h**) and (**8a-h**). Compounds (**5a-h**) and (**8a-h**) on acylation with acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid in 1 : 1 ratio yielded acetyl derivatives, (**6a-h**) and (**9a-h**) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized compounds (**5a-h**) and (**8a-h**) were screened for their antibacterial activity using cup plate diffusion method¹³. The bacterial organisms used included both Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative strains like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes*. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU ml⁻¹ and each well (diameter 10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) in DMF, so that concentration of each test compound was 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h at 37 °C, using Vernier caliper. Inhibition zone record of the compounds clearly indicated that (**5c**), (**5f**) and (**8c**), (**8f**) were highly active against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and moderately active against *S. typhi*. Majority of the compounds were found inactive against *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes* (Table 1).

To determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), the serial dilution technique¹⁴ was followed using nutrient broth medium. The MIC values of compounds (**5c**), (**5f**) and (**8c**), (**8f**), which were determined against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, found to be 70, 75 and 70, 78 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

respectively.

Screening of these compounds (**5a-h**) and (**8a-h**) having the concentration 1% and 2%, for antifungal activity using paper disc method¹⁵ showed that (**5d**), (**5g**) and (**8c**), (**8g**) were highly active against *A. niger*, whereas other compounds showed low to moderate activity. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 48 h at 37 °C (Table 1).

Experimental

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded using hot paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvents. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mull and as KBr pellete. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates by TLC.

Initially equimolar solution of benzotriazole (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxan and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (4 g) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 h, cooled and the solid obtained was

Table 1. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compounds (**5a-h**) and (**8a-h**)

Comps.	Antibacterial activity					Antifungal activity	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. aerogenes</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	
						(Conc. 1%)	(Conc. 2%)
5a	+	++	+	-	-	-	-
5b	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
5c	+++	+++	++	-	+	++	++
5d	+	-	++	+	+	+++	+++
5e	++	+	-	+	-	+	++
5f	+++	+++	++	-	-	-	+
5g	+	++	-	-	+	+++	+++
5h	-	+	++	-	-	-	+
8a	++	++	+	+	-	+	+
8b	-	+	++	+	-	-	+
8c	+++	+++	++	-	+	+++	+++
8d	++	-	-	-	+	+	++
8e	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
8f	+++	+++	++	+	-	++	++
8g	+	+	-	-	-	+++	+++
8h	+	+	++	-	+	-	+

(-) : Inactive (12 mm and less), (+) : Weakly active (13–16 mm), (++) : Moderately active (17–20 mm), (+++) : Highly active (21 mm and above).

crystallised from methanol to afford ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate. Then the parent compound, benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (**1**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of ethyl-benzotriazol-1-yl-acetate (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in 1,4-dioxan (15 ml) on a water bath for 5 h, cooled and the resulting solid was crystallised from chloroform-methanol (5 : 5 v/v) mixture, by reported method.

Synthesis of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (3a) :

The compound 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of benzotriazol-1-yl-acetic acid hydrazide (**1**) (0.01 mol) and N-phenyl isothiocyanate (**2a**) (0.01 mol) in carbontetrachloride (15 ml) for 2.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid residue obtained was crystallised from ethanol, **3a** (75%), m.p. 177 °C (Found : C, 54.98; H, 4.26; N, 25.40; S, 9.44. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₄N₆OS : C, 55.20; H, 4.32; N, 25.75; S, 9.82%); ν_{\max} 3423, 3370, 3257 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1596 (N=N), 1306 (C-N), 1247 (C=S), 1217 cm⁻¹ (N-N)¹⁶; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) : δ 8.05 (1H, s, CO-NH-N), 7.56 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.55 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.21–7.37 (5H, m, Ar-H), 3.89 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 3.81 (1H, s, CS-NH-Ar), 2.13 (1H, s, CS-NH-N); MS : *m/z* 325 (M⁺-H), 249 (M⁺-Ph), 208 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 166 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂-CO), 190 (M⁺-PhNHCS), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds (**3b-h**) using different N-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (**2b-h**) : **3b** (70%), m.p. 198 °C; **c** (72%), m.p. 169 °C; **d** (71%), m.p. 174 °C; **e** (80%), m.p. 213 °C; **f** (70%), m.p. 186 °C; **g** (81%), m.p. 170 °C; **h** (74%), m.p. 231 °C.

Synthesis of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(3,6-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-ethanone (5a) :

2-Benzotriazol-1-yl-N-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) was suspended in chloroform (15 ml). To this a solution of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.01 mol) in chloroform was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 3 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed. Then chloroform was distilled off, a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) followed by addition of ethanol, a solid acidic to litmus

was isolated, crystallised from ethanol and identified as 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(3,6-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-ethanone hydrochloride (**4a**) (78%), m.p. 218 °C. Similarly, other compounds (**4b-h**) were prepared from (**3b-h**) : **4b** (70%), m.p. 166 °C; **c** (65%), m.p. 204 °C; **d** (65%), m.p. 188 °C; **e** (80%), m.p. 227 °C; **f** (72%), m.p. 179 °C; **g** (75%), m.p. 231 °C; **h** (80%), m.p. 196 °C.

On basification of (**4a**) with dilute ammonia solution a free base was obtained, it was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (**5a**), m.p. 197 °C (Found : C, 57.11; H, 3.56; N, 21.32; S, 13.58. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₇OS₂ : C, 57.50; H, 3.73; N, 21.34; S, 13.95%); ν_{\max} 3300 (NH), 1686 (C=O), 1595 (N=N), 1573 (C=N), 1312 (C-N), 1244 (N-N), 701 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) : δ 7.52 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.49 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.25–7.45 (10H, m, Ar-H), 3.81 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.09 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR : δ 29.4(1), 112.1(2), 122.2(4), 124.1(4), 126.5(2), 128.4(2), 137.6(2), 146.4(2), 148.1(2), 163.6(1); MS : *m/z* 458 (M⁺-H), 382 (M⁺-Ph), 341 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 327 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 299 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂-CO), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other free bases (**5b-h**) : **5b**, m.p. 161 °C (Found : C, 57.95; H, 4.03; N, 20.14; S, 12.99. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₉N₇OS₂ : C, 58.33; H, 4.04; N, 20.70; S, 13.54%); ν_{\max} 3457 (NH), 1691 (C=O), 1636 (N=N), 1607 (C=N), 1247 (C-N), 1185 (N-N), 697 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆) : δ 7.59 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.53 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.18–7.41 (9H, m, Ar-H), 3.91 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.09 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR : δ 29.4(1), 31.8(1), 111.9(1), 112.8(1), 121.6(2), 122.3(1), 123.2(1), 124.4(2), 124.8(1), 125.2(1), 125.9(1), 126.2(1), 128.1(2), 137.2(2), 147.3(2), 150.8(2), 162.2(1); **c**, m.p. 192 °C (Found : C, 57.66; H, 3.99; N, 20.52; S, 13.27. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₉N₇OS₂ : C, 58.33; H, 4.04; N, 20.70; S, 13.54%); **d**, m.p. 164 °C (Found : C, 58.11; H, 3.84; N, 20.17; S, 13.47. Calcd. for C₂₃H₁₉N₇OS₂ : C, 58.33; H, 4.04; N, 20.70; S, 13.54%); **e**, m.p. 213 °C (Found : C, 53.13; H, 3.18; N, 18.83; S, 12.64. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₆N₇OS₂Cl : C, 53.49; H, 3.26; N, 19.85; S, 12.98%); **f**, m.p. 172 °C (Found : C, 52.86; H, 3.23; N, 19.78; S, 12.74. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₆N₇OS₂Cl : C, 53.49; H, 3.26; N, 19.85; S, 12.98%); **g**, m.p. 218 °C (Found : C, 53.12; H, 3.22; N,

19.67; S, 12.41. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}N_7OS_2Cl$: C, 53.49; H, 3.26; N, 19.85; S, 12.98%; **h**, m.p. 173 °C (Found : C, 54.11; H, 4.44; N, 22.05; S, 14.34. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{21}N_7OS_2$: C, 54.65; H, 4.82; N, 22.31; S, 14.59%).

Synthesis of 1-(5-acetyl-3,6-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-2-benzotriazol-1-yl-ethanone (6a) :

A mixture of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(3,6-bis-phenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-ethanone (**5a**) (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, a whitish solid precipitated was crystallised from warm water with ethanol to give (**6a**) (76%), m.p. 201 °C (Found : C, 56.95; H, 3.67; N, 19.11; S, 12.07. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{19}N_7O_2S_2$: C, 57.47; H, 3.82; N, 19.55; S, 12.78%; ν_{max} 1765, 1690 (C=O), 1635 (N=N), 1586 (C=N), 1295 (C-N), 1176 (N-N), 719 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) : δ 7.57 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.55 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.60–7.52 (10H, m, Ar-H), 3.97 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.11 (3H, s, CO-CH₃); ^{13}C NMR : δ 23.8(1), 29.4(1), 111.8(2), 121.4(4), 124.3(4), 126.5(2), 128.2(2), 137.7(2), 146.4(2), 148.2(2), 162.3(1), 163.2(1); MS : m/z 486 ($M^+ - CH_3$), 458 ($M^+ - COCH_3$), 424 ($M^+ - Ph$), 383 ($M^+ - benzotriazole$), 341 ($M^+ - benzotriazole - CH_2 - CO$), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other acetyl derivatives (**6b-h**) : **6b** (75%), m.p. 165 °C; ^{13}C NMR : δ 23.6(1), 29.3(1), 32.1(1), 111.7(1), 112.2(1), 121.1(2), 122.3(1), 123.7(1), 124.6(2), 124.8(1), 125.9(1), 126.3(1), 126.5(1), 128.4(2), 137.3(2), 147.9(2), 151.2(2), 163.1(1), 164.4(1); **c** (70%), m.p. 179 °C; **d** (80%), m.p. 198 °C; **e** (74%), m.p. 201 °C; **f** (75%), m.p. 214 °C; **g** (81%), m.p. 223 °C; **h** (78%), m.p. 187 °C.

Synthesis of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(2,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-ethanone (8a) :

2-Benzotriazol-1-yl-*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido-acetamide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) was suspended in chloroform (15 ml). To this a solution of *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride (0.01 mol) in chloroform was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 3 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed. Then chloroform was distilled off, a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), a solid acidic to litmus was isolated, crystallised from ethanol and identi-

fied as 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(2,5-bis phenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-ethanone hydrochloride (**7a**) (70%), m.p. 287 °C. Similarly, other compounds, (**7b-h**) were prepared from (**3b-h**) : **7b** (75%), m.p. 202 °C; **c** (70%), m.p. 188 °C; **d** (77%), m.p. 197 °C; **e** (70%), m.p. 167 °C; **f** (65%), m.p. 222 °C; **g** (75%), m.p. 189 °C; **h** (76%), m.p. 219 °C.

On basification of (**7a**) with dilute ammonia solution a free base was obtained, it was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, (**8a**), m.p. 277 °C (Found : C, 61.21; H, 3.93; N, 22.38; S, 7.24. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{17}N_7OS$: C, 61.81; H, 4.01; N, 22.94; S, 7.50%; ν_{max} 3393 (NH), 1652 (C=O), 1628 (N=N), 1595 (C=N), 1312 (C-N), 1214 (N-N), 693 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) : δ 7.64 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.63 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.97–7.48 (10H, m, Ar-H), 3.81 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.15 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR : δ 27.2(1), 111.8(2), 123.0(4), 124.4(4), 127.4(2), 127.9(2), 136.3(2), 143.9(2), 145.5(2), 161.6(1); MS : m/z 427 (M^+), 350 ($M^+ - Ph$), 309 ($M^+ - benzotriazole$), 267 ($M^+ - benzotriazole - CH_2 - CO$), 118 (benzotriazole⁺), 77 (Ph⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other free bases (**8b-h**) : **8b**, m.p. 185 °C (Found : C, 62.12; H, 4.13; N, 21.94; S, 7.06. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{19}N_7OS$: C, 62.57; H, 4.34; N, 22.21; S, 7.26%; ν_{max} 3440 (NH), 1646 (C=O), 1610 (N=N), 1578 (C=N), 1288 (C-N), 1248 (N-N), 706 cm^{-1} (C-S); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) : δ 7.68 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.55 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.91–7.46 (9H, m, Ar-H), 3.93 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.11 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C NMR : δ 27.7(1), 29.8(1), 111.5(1), 112.4(1), 120.4(2), 122.1(1), 122.8(1), 124.1(2), 124.5(1), 125.9(1), 126.1(1), 126.6(1), 127.8(2), 135.7(2), 145.3(2), 151.4(2), 164.3(1); **c**, m.p. 173 °C (Found : C, 61.96; H, 4.29; N, 21.94; S, 7.02. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{19}N_7OS$: C, 62.57; H, 4.34; N, 22.21; S, 7.26%); **d**, m.p. 181 °C (Found : C, 62.18; H, 4.33; N, 22.01; S, 7.13. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{19}N_7OS$: C, 62.57; H, 4.34; N, 22.21; S, 7.26); **e**, m.p. 157 °C (Found : C, 56.71; H, 3.33; N, 21.16; S, 6.88. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}N_7OSCl$: C, 57.20; H, 3.49; N, 21.23; S, 6.94%); **f**, m.p. 194 °C (Found : C, 56.91; H, 3.40; N, 20.99; S, 6.67. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}N_7OSCl$: C, 57.20; H, 3.49; N, 21.23; S, 6.94%); **g**, m.p. 167 °C (Found : C, 57.14; H, 3.38; N, 21.08; S, 6.79. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{16}N_7OSCl$: C, 57.20; H,

3.49; N, 21.23; S, 6.94); **h**, m.p. 207 °C (Found : C, 57.77; H, 5.04; N, 23.82; S, 7.77. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₇OS : C, 58.95; H, 5.19; N, 24.06; S, 7.87%).

Synthesis of 1-(4-acetyl-2,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-2-benzotriazol-1-yl-ethanone (9a) :

A mixture of 2-benzotriazol-1-yl-1-(2,5-bis-phenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-ethanone (**8a**) (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, a yellowish white solid precipitated was crystallised from warm water with ethanol to give (**9a**) (70%), m.p. 192 °C (Found : C, 61.11; H, 4.0; N, 20.33; S, 6.47. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₉N₇O₂S : C, 61.40; H, 4.08; N, 20.88; S, 6.83); ν_{\max} 1654 (C=O), 1617 (N=N), 1594 (C=N), 1318 (C-N), 1243 (N-N), 697 cm⁻¹ (C-S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 7.64 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 7.58 (2H, s, benzotriazole), 6.91–7.47 (10H, m, Ar-H), 3.93 (2H, s, N-CH₂-CO), 2.13 (3H, s, CO-CH₃); ¹³C NMR : δ 23.3(1), 27.6(1), 111.6(2), 123.7(4), 124.2(4), 126.8(2), 127.3(2), 136.1(2), 143.2(2), 144.9(2), 162.3(1), 163.8(1); MS : *m/z* 426 (M⁺-COCH₃), 392 (M⁺-Ph), 351 (M⁺-benzotriazole), 337 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂), 309 (M⁺-benzotriazole-CH₂-CO), 118 (benzotriazole⁺). This reaction was extended to synthesize other acetyl derivatives (**9b-h**) : **9b** (72%), m.p. 176 °C; ¹³C NMR : δ 23.6(1), 27.5(1), 29.6(1), 111.7(1), 112.8(1), 121.1(2), 122.3(1), 123.2(1), 124.5(2), 124.8(1), 126.2(1), 126.4(1), 126.9(1), 128.0(2), 136.2(2), 144.8(2), 149.7(2), 163.8(1), 165.2(1); **c** (75%), m.p. 212 °C; **d** (80%), m.p. 165 °C; **e** (70%), m.p. 197 °C; **f** (81%), m.p. 177 °C; **g** (68%), m.p. 204 °C; **h** (73%), m.p. 193 °C.

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